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2 Glossary

ADME: Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion

AhR: aryl hydrocarbon receptor

ALP: alkaline phosphatase

ALT: alanine aminotransferase

AST: aspartate aminotransferase

AO: adverse outcome

AR: androgen receptor

AOPs: adverse outcome pathways

ASD: autism spectrum disorders

BDNF: brain-derived neurotrophic factor

BMI: body mass index

BPA: bisphenol A

CHO: total cholesterol

CIBM: Centro de Investigación Biomédica

CpG: cytosine-phosphate-guanine island

Chromium VI: Cr(VI)

E2: estradiol

ER: estrogen receptor

FSH: follicle stimulating hormone

GDNF: glial-derived neurotrophic factor

GLU: glucose

HBM: human biomonitoring

HBM4EU: Human Biomonitoring for Europe

HDL: high density lipoprotein

HPA Axis: Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Adrenal Axis

HUSC: Hospital Universitario San Cecilio

INMA: Infancia y Medioambiente

INSERM: Institut national de la santé et de la recherche médicale

INS: insulin

KE: key event

Kim-1: kidney injury molecule-1

KISS: kisspeptin

LDL: low density lipoprotein

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LH: luteinizing hormone

NAG: N-acetyl- β -D glucosaminidase

NRC: National Research Council

MIE: molecular initiating event

MRI: magnetic resonance images

8OHdG: 8-hydroxy-2-deoxyguanosine

PFAS: perfluoroalkyl acid sulfonic

PPAR α : peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alfa

PPAR γ : peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma

QA/QC: quality analysis and control

SHBG: sex hormone-binding globulin

Sp4: transcription factor Sp4

T3: triiodo thyronine

T4: thyroxine

TNF- α : tumor necrosis factor alpha

TRY: triglycerides

TSH: thyroid stimulating hormone

TT: total testosterone

UGR: University of Granada

WHO: World Health Organization

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3 Abstract/Summary

Human biomonitoring (HBM) studies have highlighted the widespread and daily exposure to environmental chemicals, many of them being increasingly detected in human biological matrices. Some chemicals are suspected of contributing to adverse health outcomes such as reproductive, neurodevelopment, and metabolic disorders, among other developmental and chronic impairments. One of the aims of the H2020 European Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU) is the development of the field of effect biomarkers to implement them in a more systematic and harmonised way in large scale European HBM studies. The implementation of effect biomarkers complements exposure data with mechanistically based biomarkers of early and late adverse effects. For that purpose, the work package 14 has developed a step-by-step strategy to guarantee the implementation of a panel of valid effect biomarkers in HBM studies.

This work provides the full strategy procedure, from comprehensive search strategies, effect biomarkers selection criteria, classification, and prioritisation based on toxicological and adverse outcome pathway (AOP) data, to the analytical validation, implementation, and preliminary epidemiological validation. As a result, a panel of effect biomarkers was implemented in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies, including oxidative stress, reproductive and thyroid hormones in combination with novel molecular effect biomarkers, such as, the methylation and protein levels of brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) and kisspeptin (KISS), markers of neurological and reproductive health, respectively. In addition, several pilot studies have been applied. One of them that demonstrated the mediation role of BDNF effect biomarkers in the longitudinal association of childhood bisphenol A (BPA) and behavioral function of adolescents is also presented as an example.

The process developed in HBM4EU (mainly in WP14) confirms the added value of effect biomarkers in HBM and epidemiologic studies, concretely when selected and prioritised based on toxicological and clinical information. Importantly, this research work supports one of the main aims of the HBM research: to link exposure biomarkers with mechanistically-validated effect and susceptibility biomarkers to understand the public health implications of population exposure to environmental chemicals.

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4 Biomarkers: Paradigm shift in environmental health

Health alterations related to human exposure to certain environmental chemicals is one of the highest public health concerns. To describe and assess environmental chemicals exposure and their adverse health effects, epidemiological studies began to use biological markers, also known as biomarkers. This approach was born from the realisation that classical toxicological methods were not sensitive enough to identify intermediate events between the exposure and the clinical disease. As a result, exposure-effect epidemiological associations were not reliable enough to confirm the trueness of their associations. Thus, the consecutive steps that drive the exposure to a clinical disease were referred to as the **epidemiological “black box”** (Figure 1.1) (DeCaprio, 1997).

Years later, the National Research Council (NRC) divided this “black box” into a sequence of events from the exposure to the adverse effect as follows (Figure 1.2): (i) internal dose, (ii) biologically effective dose, (iii) early biological effect, and (iv) altered structure/function. Simultaneously, these events were divided into two groups; events (i) and (ii) would refer to exposure biomarkers, whereas (iii) and (iv) to effect biomarkers. The intersections between events would correspond to susceptibility biomarkers. Nevertheless, these assignments are not exclusive, since the distinction between events is often vague and they should be taken as a continuous rather than a series of different events (Grandjean, 1995).

This sequence of events can be tested and organised at toxicological level using the adverse outcome pathway (AOP) concept. AOPs are analytical constructs from toxicological studies describing the sequential chain of causally among linked events at different levels of biological organisation. The entire sequence leads to an adverse health effect (Fig 1.3).

AOPs constitute a framework to organise the toxicological information collected when assessing the adverse effect of certain environmental contaminants (e.g. phenols, parabens, polychlorinated biphenyls). Since effect biomarkers usually coincide with key events depicted in AOPs, the use of AOPs can **synergise** and align the toxicological with epidemiological knowledge, contributing to a better understanding of the biological fingerprint triggered by exposure to environmental chemicals.

Figure 1: Epidemiological ‘Black Box’ according to the classic model linking exposure with disease (1), the NRC biomarker paradigm (2), and the Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) (3). Figures 1.2 and 1.3 show the equivalence between the biomarker paradigm and their corresponding site within the AOP. Figure adapted from DeCaprio, (1997) and taken from Mustieles et al., (2020) with some modifications. ADME: Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion; MIE: Molecular initiating event; KE: Key event; AO: Adverse outcome.

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Effect biomarkers reflect alterations at molecular and/or cellular levels that occur during temporal and mechanistic pathways, thus connecting environmental chemical exposure with a potentially adverse effect on human health and eventually, a disease (Studies, 2006). However, many biomarkers are poorly understood or not fully described within the HBM context. Thus, attention should be paid to defining their properties in detail. For example, evidence regarding the temporal variation of exposure biomarkers should be obtained; and the biological meaning of the proposed effect biomarker should be validated at toxicological and analytical levels previous to its use in human biomonitoring (HBM) studies.

For a correct interpretation of the information given by biomarkers, several aspects have to be taken into account, such as the type of biomarker, the matrix in which is determined, and the moment in which is measured (Rodriguez-Carrillo, 2022). These previous steps will help for a correct interpretation of exposure-effect relationships and for a better interpretation of observed associations. The final aims continue to be those stated by the National Research Council “the ultimate objective of biomonitoring is to link information on exposures, susceptibility, and effects to understand the public health implications of exposure to environmental chemicals” (NRC, 2006).

4.1 Biomarkers of effect

Effect biomarkers are associated with a **physiological system** rather than with the toxicity of a given xenobiotic. They are defined as “*a measurable biochemical, physiological, behavioral, or other alteration in an organism that, depending on the magnitude, can be recognised as associated with an established or possible health impairment or disease*” (WHO, 2005). Consequently, they can be predictors of a physiological system (e.g. testes, brain, renal function), and they can be associated with different environmental chemicals that may affect these systems, such as bisphenols, perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), phthalates, arsenic, or chlorpyrifos among many other chemicals. In other words, effect biomarkers provide a link between the internal exposure and early and late health effects (Zare Jeddi et al., 2021).

For instance, those effect biomarkers reflecting the first results of xenobiotic-organism interactions refer to the early biological effect. Main examples within this group would be epigenetic markers, enzyme induction/inhibition, and signals of genotoxicity such as chromosomal aberrations, sister chromatid exchange, and number of mutations in the micronuclei assay. Meanwhile, effect biomarkers more representative of altered structure or function would reflect late key events and changes closer to disease onset. Consequently, a wide range of biomarkers could be found, from biochemical biomarkers such as metabolic parameters and hormones, to others markers providing quantitative information of the human body, such as the anogenital distance, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), pain assessment scales, or behavioral tests (Rodriguez-Carrillo, 2022; Ventura et al., 2021; Jeddi et al., 2021).

Given their abovementioned characteristics, effect biomarkers may enhance the identification of early effects in humans, establish dose–response relationships, identify potential modes of action, and increase the biological plausibility of epidemiological associations. Moreover, they could improve the risk assessment of a particular chemical or/and chemical mixtures (Jeddi et al., 2021).

4.2 Biomarkers of combined effect

Chemical mixtures are defined as the exposure to multiple chemicals via single or multiple sources and exposure routes, that may or may not be identifiable, and that may contribute to a joint toxicity in a target population (Bopp et al., 2018). Thus, the aim of **biomarkers of combined effect** is to map the biological effects exerted by a given mixture of environmental chemicals previously isolated from human samples, such as urine, blood, or placenta. Consequently, these kinds of

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biomarkers are also known as "biomarkers of combined internal exposure", "biomarkers of combined biological activity", or "biomarkers of *ex vivo* hormonal activity" (Vinggaard et al., 2021).

Biomarkers of combined activity can be used within an epidemiological context, providing another tool for mixture risk assessment. However, they are not useful to quantify the chemical components of a given mixture. For that purpose, effect-directed analyses should be performed (Vinggaard et al., 2021). Previous epidemiological studies have used these biomarkers to assess, for example, the effects of persistent organic pollutants in diverse human health outcomes, such as breast cancer in the adult population and, autism spectrum disorders (ASD) and risk of cryptorchidism and hypospadias in newborns. Results from these studies showed that the isolated mixtures were linked to a higher risk of breast cancer, and male urogenital malformations, respectively (Arrebola et al., 2015; Bonefeld-Jorgensen et al., 2011; Ghisari and Bonefeld-Jorgensen, 2009; Ibarluzea et al., 2004).

Figure 2: Scheme of effect-directed analysis building blocks. Extracted chemical mixture from relevant human matrices (i.e., human placenta) matrix are tested in one or more selected *in vitro/in vivo* assays. The active extract is fractionated into several subfractions and re-tested again through *in vitro* assays. The active fraction undergoes chemical analysis, afterward, tentative identification of chemicals responsible for the activity is performed. When *in vivo/in vitro* activity of the tentatively identified chemicals is confirmed, a final identification and quantification are performed. The figure is taken from Vinggaard et al., (2021) and Rodriguez-Carrillo, (2022).

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5 Purpose & Selection Criteria: Effect biomarkers

The abovementioned definition of effect biomarkers used/considered in HBM4EU project constituted the basis from which the search, identification, testing, and implementation of these markers were performed within the European (HBM4EU) project. Effect biomarkers should allow a reliable measurement of specific biological changes produced by exposure to the chemical compound of interest. Moreover, these measurements must be accurate, precise, reproducible, and interpretable.

Thus, the information provided by effect biomarkers can be used to: i) characterise inter-individual variability, ii) help to ensure that sensitive populations are identified and adequately addressed in the assessments, and iii) reduce uncertainty in the extrapolation of experimental and *in vitro* or *in vivo* data to humans. Furthermore, the ultimate purpose of effect biomarker data is the support and identification of links between exposure and epidemiological data to explore potential biological effects, leading to health outcomes.

In this regard, the HBM4EU looked for health effects elicited by exposure to prioritised chemical families, using and combining data from biomarkers of exposure to contaminants of particular interest (e.g., phthalates, bisphenols, heavy metals), and on/from biomarkers of effect. To cover this objective a series of sequential steps were needed, from literature searches, to evidence synthesis, to prioritisation based on toxicological data and analytical and physiological validation of the selected clinical and novel effect biomarkers. This strategy helped to identify, prioritise, and validate all the selected effect biomarkers before their implementation in the HBM4EU aligned studies. The entire process followed will be detailed in the following sections. All relevant information regarding search, selection criteria, validation and implementation of effect biomarkers could be additionally consulted in the HBM4EU project website: <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/> and in the following deliverables and additional deliverables: D14.1, D14.2, D14.3, D14.4, AD14.4, AD14.6, D14.7 (Olea et al; 2018, Mustieles et al., 2018, 2019; Fernandez et al., 2019, 2020, 2021; Rodriguez-Carrillo et al., 2020).

5.1 Selection Criteria

1. In order to apply biomarkers of effect in HBM studies, some specific criteria must be met. Briefly: **Non-invasive but predictive:** It must be measured in peripheral blood/serum or urine and correlated with the physiological response in the target tissue.
2. **Sensitive:** The biomarker of effect should change in response to environmental chemicals exposure in a magnitude that allows alterations to be detected.
3. **Population variability and discriminative power:** Show adequate population variability and range to be able to discriminate the health status of individuals (healthy vs. unhealthy).
4. The analytical performance of the biomarker should:
5. **Provide specific and sensitive measurements:** measurements provided must be free of potential interferences and should detect the biomarker in as many samples as possible (if the effect biomarker is poorly “expressed/concentrated” in the matrix, it would be difficult to measure).
6. **Reproducible:** Show an adequate intra- and inter-assay coefficient of variation to ensure the reproducibility of measurements..
7. Analytical and clinical validation must show that the effect biomarker is appropriate for its intended use.

Figure 3: Effect biomarkers selection criteria

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6 Process & implementation in HBM studies

A progressive strategy was developed within WP14 for searching, selecting, prioritising, validating, and implementing effect biomarkers in HBM studies. This strategy, conducted as a sequence of steps, supposed a reliable, reproducible, systematic and innovative approach for identifying biomarkers of effect. This would allow their implementation for the HBM4EU project as well as current and future HBM studies. The entire process is graphically summarised in Fig.4 and briefly explained as follows.

Figure 4: Full procedure developed in the work package 14 (WP14, HBM4EU) for the search, identification, prioritisation, validation, and implementation of effect biomarkers in HBM studies

First, a total of **14 comprehensive literature searches** were conducted in PubMed and Scopus databases, each covering one of the HBM4EU prioritised chemical families. Relevant **health outcomes** (reproduction, sexual maturation, neurodevelopment, cancer, allergies, immune system, cardiovascular diseases, obesity, and oxidative stress) and **chemical compounds** (bisphenols, cadmium, chromium IV, flame retardants, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, per-/poly-fluorinated compounds, phthalates, acrylamide, arsenic, lead, mercury, mycotoxins, pesticides, and benzophenones), already established by HBM4EU were chosen as key terms for conducting the searches (Mustieles et al., 2018:2020-D14.2,14.5). Epidemiological and/or toxicological studies that included effect biomarkers to assess the health effect of relevant chemical compounds were

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selected. Good examples of this process are the literature searches developed for bisphenols and phthalates (Baken et al., 2019; Mustieles et al., 2020).

After full-text analysis of relevant articles, the **selection criteria** were used to select potential effect biomarkers of added value for HBM studies. This process was developed in combination with the information provided by toxicological data preferentially organised following the **AOP framework**, allowing their classification according to their biological plausibility. Thus, a panel of relevant, toxicologically supported effect biomarkers was established (Table 1). Selected effect biomarkers were further classified according to their previous use in epidemiological and clinical settings as follows:

- **Classical and studied effect biomarkers:** those markers with extended knowledge of their actions in the physiological system and with extended use in clinical and epidemiological settings, such as reproductive hormones (estradiol, testosterone, follicle stimulating hormone), thyroid hormones, or markers of glucose metabolism.
- **Classical and less studied effect biomarkers:** those with previous knowledge regarding their physiological mechanism of action, but with not extended use in epidemiology, such as adipokines, inflammatory, or renal markers.
- **Novel effect biomarkers:** those with not extended use in a clinical, nor epidemiological settings, such as kisspeptin, brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), gene expression of nuclear receptor, epigenetic markers, and genetic polymorphisms.

An inventory of effect biomarkers according to the human developmental window explored in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies (e.g. childhood, adolescence, and adulthood) was firstly developed (available in AD14.3). The prioritisation of effect biomarkers was done according to the aforementioned inventory, **gaps in knowledge** identified during the comprehensive literature searches, their toxicological relevance provided by AOP information, and the sample availability of the Aligned Studies. Thus, **BDNF** was selected as a **novel effect biomarker** for neurodevelopment, and **kisspeptin** for reproductive disorders. Their protein levels and DNA methylation patterns were set as main targets for the validation analyses. Moreover, to complement the information provided by these novel effect biomarkers, some **classical biomarkers** were also prioritised according to their implication in BDNF and kisspeptin signaling cascades (consulting potential AOPs) and their epidemiological evidence. Thus, thyroid hormones, reproductive hormones, glucose metabolism, serum lipids, and oxidative stress markers were selected for their analytical and physiological validation as well (Table 1).

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Table 1: Panel of effect biomarkers considered for their implementation in the HBM aligned studies

Effect Biomarkers		
Classical (studied)	Classical (less studied)	Novel
Reproductive Hormones: estradiol (E2), total testosterone (TT), follicle stimulating hormone (FSH), luteinising hormone (LH), sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG).	HPArenal-Axis: cortisol	Kisspeptin
Thyroid Hormones: thyroxine (T4), triiodo thyronine (T3), thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH)	Adipokines: leptin and adiponectin	Gene expression of nuclear receptors: peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma (PPAR γ), estrogen receptor (ER), androgen receptor (AR), aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR).
Glucose metabolism: insulin (INS), glucose (GLU), HOMA-IR.	Inflammatory markers: tumor necrotic factor (TNF- α), interleukin 1, 6, etc.	Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), glial-derived neurotrophic factor (GDNF), transcription factor Sp4 (Sp4).
Serum lipids: total cholesterol (CHO), high density lipoprotein (HDL), low density lipoprotein (LDL), triglycerides (TRY).	Liver enzymes: aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), bilirubin, albumin	Epigenetic markers: DNA methylation, histones modifications.
Blood pressure: systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure.	Renal function: N-acetyl- β -D glucosaminidase (NAG), Kim-1: kidney injury molecule-1 (Kim-1)	Genetic polymorphisms

HPA Axis: Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Adrenal Axis

The analytical validation of proposed effect biomarkers should fulfill a number of requisites. The available methodology should be sensitive, reliable, reproducible, and economically affordable. In that manner, the measurement of effect biomarkers would provide a correct quality of the data by reducing potential error vials. Consequently, strict quality analysis and control (QA/QC) protocols were designed, especially for novel effect biomarkers. A full explanation of the QA/QC protocols, conducted in HBM4EU, is detailed elsewhere (Rodriguez-Carrillo et al., 2019; Fernandez et al., 2020). Protein levels of novel and classical effect biomarkers were measured using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays, for which maximum inter- and intra-coefficient of variations were set to 5 and 15%, respectively. Additionally, samples were measured in duplicate and in different assay batch, to then calculate the mean of both values further reducing assay variability to the minimum (Fig. 5).

Further, DNA methylation patterns of BDNF and kisspeptin genes were conducted through the gold-standard bisulfite pyrosequencing analyses in the *Institute National de la Santé et de la Recherche Médicale* (INSERM), France, applying strict quality control used in molecular biology (samples showed 1.8–1.9 ratio at 260/280 absorbance, indicating optimal DNA purification). Classical effect biomarkers were measured in the laboratory of San Cecilio University Hospital (HUSC), located in Granada (Spain), and novel effect biomarkers in the facilities of the Biomedical Research Centre (CIBM) of the Granada University, Spain.

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After the prioritisation, selection, and the analytical validation of effect biomarkers, the next step was clear: to assess their physiological validation for epidemiological purposes before their implementation in HBM4EU aligned studies. This will be discussed in the following chapter.

Figure 5: Esqueme of quality control procedure to measure effect biomarkers concentrations.

6.1 Existing Europeans cohorts

During the literature searches performed by WP14, an important gap in knowledge regarding the neurological effect of BPA was found. As BDNF appeared as a promising effect biomarker to cover this gap, a post-hoc search in the AOP-Wiki (<https://aopwiki.org/>) was performed looking for AOPs under the search term "decreased BDNF" (Mustieles et al., 2020). From that additional search, three AOPs were identified and merged, thus establishing an AOP network. Finally, each key event included in the AOP network was consulted in all available *in vivo* studies addressing BPA exposure and BDNF. With this process the connection of BPA exposure and neurodevelopmental alterations through alterations on BDNF secretion patterns was supported from a biological perspective (Mustieles et al., 2020) (Figure 6).

To examine the physiological validity of this effect biomarker in epidemiological settings, WP14 developed a series of **pilot studies** to assess the impact of bisphenol A (BPA) on the neurobehavioral function of adolescents (an understudied period of development). According to this, blood DNA methylation of the BDNF gene Exon IV at six CpGs was measured. Further, protein levels of total serum and urine BDNF were quantified to test this biomarker at different levels of biological organisation. All biomarkers were implemented in adolescent males (15-17 yrs.) from the INMA-Granada (*Infancia y Medioambiente*) birth cohort. In this population, urine BPA concentrations measured at 9-11 years were available.

Figure 6: AOP network extracted from the search performed in the AOP-Wiki under the term “decreased BDNF”. Figure taken from Mustieles et al., (2020)

Therefore, WP14 conducted a longitudinal pilot study to ascertain:

- The longitudinal association of childhood BPA with the behavioral function during adolescence.
- The longitudinal association between childhood BPA and BDNF effect biomarkers during adolescence.
- The cross-sectional association between BDNF effect biomarkers and adolescent’s behavioral function.
- The mediation role of BDNF in the potential BPA-Behavioral function association.

Results showed that higher BPA concentrations were associated with more thought problems among male adolescents from the INMA-Granada cohort (Figure 7.A brown-color bars). Additionally, higher BPA concentration were associated with higher BDNF gene DNA methylation in general and particularly at CpG6 (Figure 7.A blue-color bars). Higher BDNF CpG6 DNA methylation was cross-sectionally and dose-dependently associated with thought problems (Figure 7.A green-color bars). Moreover, BDNF methylation at CpG6 mediated up to 34% of the BPA-thought problems association (Figure 7.B). Therefore, it seems that BDNF could be a valuable effect biomarker for the neurodevelopmental alterations produced by BPA during childhood. Nevertheless, more studies with higher sample size and longitudinal designs should be performed to confirm these results (Mustieles et al., 2022).

Figure 7: Main results from the pilot study developed in the INMA-Granada cohort with adolescent males (15/17 yrs.). (A) Longitudinal, positive, dose-dependent association between childhood BPA with thought problems and BDNF gene DNA methylation at CpG6. Cross-sectional, positive, dose-dependent association between BDNF gene DNA methylation at CpG6 and thought problems. (B) Mediation analysis showing the mediation role of BDNF gene DNA methylation at CpG6 in the association between childhood BPA and thought problems that account for up to 34 %.

6.2 HBM4EU-Occupational studies

In the framework of the HBM4EU project, we also focus on better understanding the determinants of exposure and the human effect of work-related exposures in industrial hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)) processing (chromium plating, surface treatment and welding). Cr(VI) enters cells due to high membrane permeability to its solubilised forms and is toxic due to its ability to oxidise through reactive oxygen species (ROS) produced by the intracellular detoxification process. In addition, it acts through direct and indirect genotoxic mechanisms, as both Cr(IV) and Cr(V) can form premutagenic DNA and DNA-protein adducts and ROS can contribute to the formation of DNA single and double strand breaks, leading to genetic instability. Cr(VI) is an occupational carcinogen that has been shown to cause lung cancer, as well as to be associated with nasal and sinus cancer in man, as well as with other serious adverse effects (Santonen et al., 2022).

The Chromates occupational study was developed with the main aim of providing multi-national EU-relevant data on Cr(VI) (nine European countries) internal exposure to

Figure 8: Stars in the map show countries participating in this occupational study.

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hexavalent chromium [Cr(VI)] (Figure 8). The use of Cr(VI) compounds (e.g. chromates and chromium trioxide) is authorised under the European regulation (EC 1907/2006) REACH and there is no alternative to the Cr(VI) use so far. The exposure occurs mainly by inhalation during occupational activities such as welding, Cr(VI) electroplating, and other surface treatment activities. Nevertheless, dermal contact may be relevant as well.

Therefore, efforts have been made to search for new indicators, allowing for the deeper assessment of adverse effects and the risk of health effects. HBM and occupational hygiene data were collected from 399 workers and 203 controls. The aim of this initiative was also characterising conventional and more promising early effect biomarkers in blood and urine samples collected from workers and controls, in order to explore the potential relationship between exposure, early biological effects and health outcomes. Effect biomarkers characterised included classical and novel biomarkers such as the alkaline comet assay, the cytokinesis-block micronucleus assay in peripheral blood leukocytes and reticulocytes, urinary oxidative stress markers (malondialdehyde, and 8-oxo-2'-deoxyguanosine), global methylation in DNA from leukocytes and metabolomics in urine matrices.

The highest internal exposures showed among participants (assessed by the urinary Cr level) were related to the use of Cr(VI) in electrolytic bath plating. Conversely, welding activities were associated with the lowest internal exposure, may due to the lower bioavailability of Cr(VI) species formed during welding. A high correlation was observed between urinary chromium levels and exposure to Cr(VI) in air or total Cr on skin. Urinary chromium was shown to be the best proxy for the assessment of total internal human exposure. Furthermore, low correlations were found between urinary chromium and Cr(VI) in red blood cells, probably due to differences in kinetics, indicating that both biomonitoring approaches are necessary and complementary.

Genotoxicity biomarkers in blood cells revealed that workers in electrolytic bath plating display the highest levels of DNA and chromosomal damage in leukocytes and the second highest level of chromosomal damage in reticulocytes. Additionally, welders exhibited the highest frequency of micronuclei in reticulocytes despite the lower urinary Cr levels, suggesting recent exposure to Cr(VI) that might not have been captured by post-shift urinary Cr levels.

The frequency of micronucleated lymphocytes was significantly related to the urinary Cr level with the highest exposed group (3rd tercile of Cr level in urine) displaying the highest frequency of micronucleated cells. The micronucleus frequency in reticulocytes was also related to the urinary Cr level. Data of genotoxicity biomarkers also evidenced that controls recruited within the industries (e.g., office workers) displayed levels of genotoxic damage much higher than those of controls recruited outside the companies. Thus, findings highlight the possibility of a bystander effect in office workers from companies where Cr(VI) is used. Furthermore, when comparing global DNA methylation levels between exposed and control groups showed a statistically significant decrease in the levels observed in workers, suggesting deregulation of gene expression.

The non-targeted metabolomics method of ultra high-performance liquid chromatography-quadrupole time-of-flight mass spectrometry (UHPLC-QTOF-MS) for quantitative analysis of low-molecular-weight metabolites was used for the identification of significant metabolic differences that could better explain the metabolic, physiological and pathological mechanisms of Cr(VI) toxicity. Significantly different metabolites abundance was detected depending on the studied worker's subgroups with exposure to Cr(VI). The greatest number of putatively annotated metabolites belonged to pathways of amino acids, especially tryptophan and tyrosine metabolism, fatty acids and sub pathway arachidonic acid metabolism, as well as the metabolism of carbohydrates and carbohydrate conjugates, vitamins, hormones, nicotine, and oxidative phosphorylation. Changes in abundance of urinary excreted metabolites observed in workers could

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be due from work-related factors, other than Cr(VI) exposure. Further targeted metabolomics studies are needed to better understand the observed modifications and further explore the suitability of urinary metabolites as early indicators of adverse effects associated with exposure to Cr(VI) (Kozłowska et al., 2022).

In summary, early identification of work-related health effects is largely possible when biomarkers of effects, supported by mechanistic knowledge, are integrated together with biomarkers of exposure and characterisation of the work environment. Moreover, these effect biomarkers provide a new perspective for understanding the molecular mechanism of metal toxicity and predicting its health effects. Priority should be given to the groups at highest risk (based on both exposure and effect biomarkers) and mitigation measures should be taken for them.

These data should be used as scientific evidence for risk assessment and regulatory decision-making in the framework of EU chemical legislation and occupational safety and health legislation.

6.3 HBM4EU-Aligned studies

Classical and novel effect biomarkers were measured in blood and urine samples of children and teenage populations from different European studies, which are known as the HBM4EU Aligned studies. All data analyses are currently ongoing and only very preliminary results are available. A description of this approach is summarised as follows:

Data regarding children exposure to phthalates and flame retardants as well as their neurodevelopmental state (behavioral function, measured with the Child Behavior Check List; cognitive function, measured with the Wechsler's Intelligence Scale for Children) was available. Additionally, DNA methylation and protein levels of BDNF were measured in blood and serum samples, respectively. Moreover, thyroid, and reproductive hormones were ascertained as well to cover the entire adverse outcome pathway (Figure 9).

Data regarding adolescent's exposure to phthalates and PFAS as well as their sexual maturation and metabolism function (Tanner's stage scale for sexual maturation; lipid and glucose markers for metabolism function and BMI) was available. Additionally, DNA methylation (*KISS1* gene) and protein levels of kisspeptin (kisspeptin 54/kiss54) were measured in blood and serum samples, respectively (Figure 9). Data analyses are currently ongoing. Although interesting results begin to appear, results have not been reported in this work due to possible copyright and overlapping problems with the peer-review publication of these works in the coming months.

Figure 9: Graphical summary of exposure and effect biomarkers measured so far in the Aligned studies together with their respective outcomes according to age.

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7 Lessons learnt

Main lessons learnt from the last 5 years of research could be summarised in the following bullet points and chapters:

- WP14 partners and collaborators have created an organised a scientific corpus of information on effect biomarkers synergising toxicological, analytical and epidemiological points of view.
- Effect biomarkers, when appropriately selected based on adverse outcome pathways, toxicological and clinical knowledge can provide a critical added value to HBM studies.
- When used together with exposure biomarkers in occupational and population settings, effect biomarkers can greatly contribute to risk assessment and management, leading to better protection of human health.
- The main basis and concepts are now settled-down, and the first systematic and harmonised implementation of effect biomarkers has been performed in the HBM4EU aligned and occupational studies.
- More work needs to be done in future projects like PARC (European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals) to increase the uptake of effect biomarker data into risk assessment.
- The HBM4EU chromates study has shown that even at low levels of CrVI exposure (<5 µg/m³ for work-places), some biological adverse effects including carcinogenicity cannot be excluded.
- The implementation of biomarkers of early biological (genotoxic or epigenetic) effects, measured in blood cells, can help establish a causal relationship between exposure and carcinogenic effects in occupational settings.
- HBM4EU chromates study has shown that effect biomarkers are useful for identifying the occupational activities at highest risk and those for which mitigation measures should be prioritised (**high-risk settings**).

7.1 Importance of the chosen matrix for effect biomarker measurement

Biomonitoring provides unequivocal evidence that the exposure, the uptake, and a potential adverse effect have taken place. Importantly, biological samples in HBM should be easily accessible under routine conditions and without health risk for the individual. For these reasons, blood and urine samples are the most widely used and accepted matrices for evaluating environmental chemicals in occupational and environmental toxicology (Gil and Hernández, 2015).

The measurement of a xenobiotic metabolite in a target biological matrix reflects the amount of xenobiotic that has been metabolised by the organism. It brings information regarding the magnitude and the time of the exposure. The same concept can be applied to effect biomarkers since the biological meaning of a given effect biomarker could change based on the matrix chosen, constituting an important decision.

The characteristics of the most suitable matrix should be based on its feasibility, invasiveness, volume availability, storage, and processing requirements, and the predictive value of the effect biomarkers measured. Ideally, priority will be given to those samples with an easy collection and storage process, preferably as less invasive as possible and with a previous validation of the biological meaning of the measured effect biomarker. Although some effect biomarkers are more indicated in urine, for most effect biomarkers, blood represent the key matrix to target since it can provide a source of genetic polymorphisms (susceptibility biomarkers), epigenetic (DNA

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methylation, histones, micro-RNAs), and protein levels. Notwithstanding, this requires an effort to harmonise the processing of blood samples, preservation of RNA and micro-RNA materials with specific reagents, and storage at -80°C with the minimum number of thaw-freeze cycles possible. Future projects should consider the development of harmonised protocols for sample processing, preservation, and storage to allow the implementation of effect biomarkers under the highest quality standards.

7.2 Strengths and Limitations

The entire procedure to find, select, prioritise, validate, and implement effect biomarkers in HBM studies, owns several strengths, but also limitations. First, although the search strategies followed a comprehensive approach, they might not cover all relevant effect biomarkers. Notwithstanding, the fact that 14 independent literature searches were performed minimises the risk of not accounting for a relevant effect biomarker in the general inventory generated (AD14.3 and Zare-Jeddi et al., 2021). Second, effect biomarkers are not specific of particular chemical exposures, thus increasing uncertainty when analysing exposure-effect associations. Nevertheless, the toxicological and AOP-driven prioritisation procedure allowed to validate the use of effect biomarkers for specific chemical families. This is for example exemplified by the BPA-BDNF pilot case study developed in the INMA-Granada cohort, that increases the confidence of our approach. Third, there are several gaps in knowledge, such as for example the still scarce availability of AOPs in the AOP Wiki, that can limit the use of toxicological data to prioritise effect biomarkers for some health outcomes not yet covered. However, even if a fully-developed AOP is not found, we have shown that it is still possible to gather the toxicological data available and construct preliminary or putative AOPs that can both help to select effect biomarkers and may represent a first stimulus to develop that specific AOP in the near future. So, the bidirectional feedback between effect biomarkers and the field of AOPs, will likely lead to improvements in both directions. Fourth, the biological meaning of effect biomarkers could change according to the matrix in which is measured; thus, a careful validation procedure must be made. The approach followed in HBM4EU for novel markers has been to measure the prioritised effect biomarkers at different levels of biological organisation: for example, BDNF was measured in blood (DNA methylation), serum (protein level) and urine (protein level), allowing to compare performance among matrices. Fifth, we followed a targeted effect biomarker approach. While the advantage is that we have followed a robust approach for the prioritisation of effect biomarkers, the limitation is that we can lose other adverse effects not mapped by the specific effect biomarkers implemented. In this regard, high-throughput and non-targeted approaches could be used in complementation to the proposed targeted strategy, since they enable the analysis of multiple targets at different levels, (genes, proteins, and metabolites) and the identification of potential effect-specific profiles, thus providing possible new information and hypotheses on gene networks, cell signaling pathways, and/or modes of action.

Among the strengths, we should highlight the careful step-to-step strategy since it enables the selection of potential effect biomarkers in a systematic and standardised manner. Additionally, the selection criteria enhance the selection of effect biomarkers, and the validation procedure at analytical and epidemiological levels increase the confidence and reproducibility of measurements. The feedback established between effect biomarkers and toxicological information organised in AOPs is one of the main strengths of this procedure, since it guarantees the biological meaning of effect biomarkers as events of the exposure-effect-adverse outcome relationship. Additionally, the classification of effect biomarkers and creation of an inventory (partially showed in Table 1, AD14.3, Zare-Jeddi et al., 2021) is also a major strength, since it sets a framework and scientific corpus that will be useful for future HBM studies. As concrete examples, the toxicological-driven hypothesis performed in the pilot study with BPA, BDNF, and behavioral function serves as

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example of how effect biomarkers should be validated for HBM purposes, although the same results should be replicated in other studies with broader sample sizes. Another example is the importance of implementation effect biomarkers in occupational settings to predict possible carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic effects, serving as an early warning signal to improve safety protocols and mitigation measures in a timely way.

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8 Conclusion

The work done in HBM4EU (WP14) confirms the added value of including effect biomarkers in HBM and epidemiologic studies, especially when selected and prioritised based on toxicological and clinical information, providing a structured framework to implement effect biomarkers in a more harmonised and systematic manner in HBM studies. Among the advantages of implementing effect biomarkers together with exposure biomarkers are: i) the evaluation of potential adverse effects in a timely -and/or early- manner (especially relevant for new chemicals and substitutes, and for diseases with a long-latency period); ii) the possibility to align the toxicological and epidemiological knowledge, consequently improving the biological plausibility of the associations investigated, and increasing the chances of uptake by regulatory bodies; iii) a higher degree of causal inference through the performance of mediation analyses in longitudinal settings; iv) the assessment of dose-response relationships; and even v) to adopt mitigation measures for human groups at highest health risk (based on biomarkers of exposure and effect). Overall, this work sets the ground to materialise one of the main aims of the HBM research: to link exposure biomarkers with mechanistically-validated effect and susceptibility biomarkers to better understand the public health implications of population exposure to environmental chemicals.

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9 References

- Arrebola, J.P., Molina-Molina, J.M., Fernández, M.F., Sáenz, J.M., Amaya, E., Indiveri, P., Hill, E.M., Scholze, M., Orton, F., Kortenkamp, A., Olea, N., 2015. A novel biomarker for anti-androgenic activity in placenta reveals risks of urogenital malformations. *Reproduction* 149, 605–13. <https://doi.org/10.1530/REP-14-0525>
- Baken, K.A., Lambrechts, N., Remy, S., Mustieles, V., Rodríguez-Carrillo, A., Neophytou, C.M., Olea, N., Schoeters, G., 2019. A strategy to validate a selection of human effect biomarkers using adverse outcome pathways: Proof of concept for phthalates and reproductive effects. *Environ. Res.* 175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.05.013>
- Bonefeld-Jorgensen, E.C., Long, M., Bossi, R., Ayotte, P., Asmund, G., Krüger, T., Ghisari, M., Mulvad, G., Kern, P., Nzulumiki, P., Dewailly, E., 2011. Perfluorinated compounds are related to breast cancer risk in Greenlandic Inuit: a case control study. *Environ. Health* 10, 88. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1476-069X-10-88>
- Bopp, S.K., Barouki, R., Brack, W., Dalla Costa, S., Dorne, J.-L.C.M., Drakvik, P.E., Faust, M., Karjalainen, T.K., Kephelopoulos, S., van Klaveren, J., Kolossa-Gehring, M., Kortenkamp, A., Lebet, E., Lettieri, T., Nørager, S., Rüegg, J., Tarazona, J. V., Trier, X., van de Water, B., van Gils, J., Bergman, Å., 2018. Current EU research activities on combined exposure to multiple chemicals. *Environ. Int.* 120, 544–562. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2018.07.037>
- DeCaprio, A.P., 1997. Biomarkers: Coming of Age for Environmental Health and Risk Assessment. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 31, 1837–1848. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es960920a>
- Ghisari, M., Bonefeld-Jorgensen, E.C., 2009. Effects of plasticizers and their mixtures on estrogen receptor and thyroid hormone functions. *Toxicol. Lett.* 189, 67–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2009.05.004>
- Gil, F., Hernández, A.F., 2015. Toxicological importance of human biomonitoring of metallic and metalloid elements in different biological samples. *Food Chem. Toxicol.* 80, 287–297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2015.03.025>
- Grandjean, P., 1995. Biomarkers in epidemiology. *Clin. Chem.* 41, 1800–1803. <https://doi.org/10.1093/CLINCHEM/41.12.1800>
- Ibarluzea, J.M., Fernández, M.F., Santa-Marina, L., Olea-Serrano, M.F., Rivas, A.M., Aurrekoetxea, J.J., Expósito, J., Lorenzo, M., Torné, P., Villalobos, M., Pedraza, V., Sasco, A.J., Olea, N., 2004. Breast Cancer Risk and the Combined Effect of Environmental Estrogens. *Cancer Causes Control* 15, 591–600. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:CACO.0000036167.51236.86>
- Kozłowska, L., Santonen, T., Duca, R.C., Godderis, L., Jagiello, K., Janasik, B., Van Nieuwenhuyse, A., Poels, K., Puzyn, T., Scheepers, P.T.J., Sijko, M., Silva, M.J., Sosnowska, A., Viegas, S., Verdonck, J., Wąsowicz, W., on behalf of HBM4EU Chromates Study Team, on behalf of Statistical Team, 2022. HBM4EU Chromates Study: Urinary Metabolomics Study of Workers Exposed to Hexavalent Chromium. *Metab.* 2022, Vol. 12, Page 362 12, 362. <https://doi.org/10.3390/METABO12040362>
- Mustieles, V., D’Cruz, S.C., Couderq, S., Rodríguez-Carrillo, A., Fini, J.-B., Hofer, T., Steffensen, I.-L., Dirven, H., Barouki, R., Olea, N., Fernández, M.F., David, A., 2020. Bisphenol A and its analogues: A comprehensive review to identify and prioritize effect biomarkers for human biomonitoring. *Environ. Int.* 144, 105811. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.105811>
- Mustieles, V., Rodríguez-Carrillo, A., Vela-Soria, F., D’Cruz, S.C., David, A., Smagulova, F., Mundo-López, A., Olivas-Martínez, A., Reina-Pérez, I., Olea, N., Freire, C., Arrebola, J.P., Fernández, M.F., 2022. BDNF as a potential mediator between childhood BPA exposure and behavioral function in adolescent boys from the INMA-Granada cohort. *Sci. Total Environ.*

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803, 150014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCITOTENV.2021.150014>

Rodriguez-Carrillo, A., 2022. Effect Biomarkers in Human Biomonitoring Programs [WWW Document]. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32224.97287>

Santonen, T., Porras, S.P., Bocca, B., Bousoumah, R., Duca, R.C., Galea, K.S., Godderis, L., Göen, T., Hardy, E., Iavicoli, I., Janasik, B., Jones, K., Leese, E., Leso, V., Louro, H., Majery, N., Ndaw, S., Pinhal, H., Ruggieri, F., Silva, M.J., van Nieuwenhuysse, A., Verdonck, J., Viegas, S., Wasowicz, W., Sepai, O., Scheepers, P.T.J., Aimonen, K., Antoine, G., Anzion, R., Burgart, M., Castaño, A., Cattaneo, A., Cavallo, D.M., De Palma, G., Denis, F., Gambelunghe, A., Gomes, B., Hanser, O., Helenius, R., Ladeira, C., López, M.E., Lovreglio, P., Marsan, P., Melczer, M., Nogueira, A., Pletea, E., Poels, K., Remes, J., Ribeiro, E., Santos, S.R., Schaefers, F., Spankie, S., Spoek, R., Rizki, M., Rousset, D., van Dael, M., Veijalainen, H., 2022. HBM4EU chromates study - Overall results and recommendations for the biomonitoring of occupational exposure to hexavalent chromium. *Environ. Res.* 204, 111984. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVRES.2021.111984>

Studies, L., 2006. Human Biomonitoring for Environmental Chemicals. <https://doi.org/10.17226/11700>

Ventura, C., Gomes, B.C., Oberemm, A., Louro, H., Huuskonen, P., Mustieles, V., Fernández, M.F., Ndaw, S., Mengelers, M., Luijten, M., Gundacker, C., Silva, M.J., 2021. Biomarkers of effect as determined in human biomonitoring studies on hexavalent chromium and cadmium in the period 2008–2020. *Environ. Res.* 197, 110998. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVRES.2021.110998>

Vinggaard, A.M.A.M., Bonfeld-Jørgensen, E.C.E.C., Jensen, T.K.T.K., Fernandez, M.F.M.F., Rosenmai, A.K.A.K., Taxvig, C., Rodriguez-Carrillo, A., Wielsøe, M., Long, M., Olea, N., Antignac, J.-P.J.-P., Hamers, T., Lamoree, M., 2021. Receptor-based in vitro activities to assess human exposure to chemical mixtures and related health impacts 146, 106191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.106191>

Zare Jeddi, M., Hopf, N.B., Viegas, S., Price, A.B., Paini, A., van Thriel, C., Benfenati, E., Ndaw, S., Bessems, J., Behnisch, P.A., Leng, G., Duca, R.C., Verhagen, H., Cubadda, F., Brennan, L., Ali, I., David, A., Mustieles, V., Fernandez, M.F., Louro, H., Pasanen-Kase, R., 2021. Towards a systematic use of effect biomarkers in population and occupational biomonitoring. *Environ. Int.* 146, 106257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVINT.2020.106257>